

BancoWeb interaction and management tools - new features for breast phantom image database

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Abstract— BancoWeb is an image database designed mainly to aid research in the field of mammography images digital processing. Developed originally with a management system providing conditions to choose and download high quality mammographic images, it affords currently also some tools that expand the database resources beyond a single image download for tests. Its search engine is of freely access online and it has been improved, changed and incorporating new resources in the last few years. In this article, we focus on incorporating a novel feature of this system into managing a new breast phantom images database added to the original set of actual mammography images. Characteristics regarding the phantom and their corresponding images, such as the possibility of random distribution of simulated lesions as well as the background texture, are presented together with the new resources for registering, searching and downloading these images implemented in the new module of the management system. In addition, a comparison of the characteristics of BancoWeb is made with other known databases in the world.

Keywords—*mammography images database, breast phantom, database management system, CADx schemes*

I. INTRODUCTION

Validation and evaluation of computer-aided diagnosis (CADx) schemes in mammography [1] is usually performed by testing images from databases used as ground truth in statistical rate surveys of true-positive (PV), true-negative (VN), false-positive (FP) and false-negative (FN) cases. The relation between these rates using ROC [2] or FROC curves gives an estimate of the sensitivity and specificity of such schemes performance.

Some databases should have radiological reports and/or biopsy confirmation reports for each case and preferably, images should be of high contrast and good quality, with adequate spatial resolution and no compression of the digital file. Another important requirement for mammography databases is large amount of images with a wide variety of cases, i.e. images with findings such as microcalcifications, suspicious masses, asymmetries and architectural distortions, including examples of normal mammograms. Moreover, for these bases of universal use, it would be useful free access to the files [3].

Mammographic databases widely used for testing processing schemes, DDSM [4] and MIAS [5], for example, have some limitations that may today disadvantage the use of their cases. MIAS contains low-contrast scanned images and an unbalanced number of malignant and benign findings among its cases. Although extensive and well documented, DDSM does not have sufficient accuracy in findings outline, making it difficult to validate lesion segmentation algorithms. Furthermore, DDSM is no longer being updated.

Therefore, researchers in the field often develop their own databases to evaluate computational schemes, often with restricted access to research team members [3,6,7].

An alternative is the use of both physical and computationally synthesized mammographic phantoms [8,9]. The main problem however is that most of physical phantoms always corresponded to the same type of structure [10]. On the one hand, it does not allow obtaining a significant number of different images and, on the other, it can induce the computational scheme to get adapted in the constant internal characteristics so that it always get detecting the existing structures of interest.

Previous research [11,12] has developed an innovative breast phantom, especially designed to be used to evaluate the behavior of computational aid tools either for detecting relevant findings or for their interpretation. Many exposures of such phantom have provided a number of images as well as their corresponding gold standard, that is, the map information on the type and location of simulated internal structures. Its main characteristic is that simulated nodules and/or clusters of microcalcifications can be randomly located into the phantom layers hence generating a large amount of different images.

Our database, called “BancoWeb”[13], has been developed during about two decades, being composed by thousands of mammography images carefully digitized from film mammograms. Part of the whole set of images is available for free access on line [13]. Another set of new tools had to be implemented in this system in order to incorporate the managing of mentioned breast phantom images.

Thus, this paper addresses the description of such tools as well as the aspects regarding the availability of phantom images obtained in DR mammography equipment to be incorporated into the database along with other actual digital mammography images also obtained in FFDM systems.

II. METHODS AND MATERIALS

One of the new tools implemented in the database was management for archiving and handling (and eventually downloading) images from the recently developed breast phantom [12]. This phantom consists of eight layers composed of paraffin gel with submerged PVC film in a non-uniform distribution, and three layers composed only of paraffin gel. Such distribution allows simulating more or less dense regions, according to the material concentration, resulting in the four BI-RADS® density classification categories. The nodules were simulated using two printed three-dimensional models, one for circumscribed lesions

and one for spiculated lesions. For microcalcifications, granulated hydroxyapatite distributed in four clusters representing cases commonly found in actual breasts [14] was used. Each lesion is also inserted physically over the phantom image as well as also using a computational tool adding the lesion radiographic image to the simulated breast image. In this case, intensity and location of each lesion may vary depending on the user's choice. Fig. 1 illustrates the phantom structures and a typical image.

Fig. 1. (a) Phantom and its layers (paraffin gel, left, and paraffin + PVC film, right); (b) 3D models of nodules; (c) cluster of granulated hydroxyapatite simulating microcalcifications; (d) example of a phantom image with simulated lesions. (Source: [12])

The main characteristic of this phantom is its flexibility in representing a very large number of different radiographic projections, such as simulating a very large number of different mammographic images. As a result, this feature makes it possible to generate a statistically significant amount of different images representing suspicious or “benign” structures, stored for use in tests of development and performance of CADE / CADx schemes [12].

With a view to the creation of a unique module for all these phantom images, menus were created to register equipment, findings, phantom image, and tools to phantom image searching with appropriate adjustments to the records and image profile. In addition to tables corresponding to such new menus, a field was added to register the type of finding in order to distinguish the common findings in actual breast images recorded in the database from the set of phantom images.

At the registration of each phantom image a set of information provided is recorded, as: (a) description, distribution and type of signal (nodule or clustered microcalcifications present at the referent image); (b) mammography equipment used during the phantom exposure (images were obtained from exposures in DR and CR systems, as HOLOGIC Dimensions, GE Senographe DS, and LORAD M-IV with CR Agfa 85); (c) X-ray exposure characteristics, as selected target/filter at the tube, preprocessing mode (when available), kVp, mAs, compression; (d) and phantom characteristics during the exposure for each image, as intensity of each inserted lesion, radiographic density, phantom configuration and the

associate template – the image containing information on the precise location of each simulated lesion – for reference.

In order to discriminate the records corresponding to actual breast images from the new phantom images, a “Belongs to” field has been created allowing to select whether the type of finding is in an actual or phantom image.

Image search menu allows exploring any set of information. The phantom image search has 4 blocks divided into: equipment data, hospital data, phantom signal information and image data (target/filter combination, preprocessing, image name, phantom configuration, kVp, mAs, compression, density and intensity of the lesion), as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 shows a screenshot of a database search interface. At the top, there are two dropdown menus: 'Equipment Data' (set to 'All') and 'Hospital Data' (set to 'All'). Below these is a 'Phantom Finder Information' section with a dropdown menu set to 'All'. The main part of the interface is an 'Image Data' table with the following fields: Target Filter, Preprocessing, Image Name, Phantom Configuration, kVp, mAs, Compression (cm), Density (%), and Intensity of injury. At the bottom right, there are 'MENU' and 'SEARCH' buttons.

Fig. 2. Page in the database management scheme corresponding to the phantom image search menu.

When using this menu, an internal procedure displays a list of results corresponding to the images with such chosen characteristics available within the database (see Fig. 3). Spreading out a single image, all information recorded in the database about that case is displayed as a searching return.

When selecting the template button a screen containing the template (reference) image corresponding to the phantom image displayed is exhibited. Alternatively the “More Information” button can be selected so that the phantom image, the respective template, and information on the equipment, image source, system, hospital, findings (with respective distribution and type), phantom layers configuration, target/filter combination, preprocessing filter, kVp, mAs, compression, density and lesion intensity, are displayed in the same screen as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). This same return screen allows downloading all the cases, that is, images and information (in .txt format), all files compressed into a .RAR file.

The Image Profile menu displays options for viewing graphs of statistics relative, for instance, to number and type of signals of interest together or separately by actual or phantom images (Fig. 4b). Also a page explaining the phantom constitution can be displayed depending on the user interest.

Fig. 3. Typical return screen from the phantom images searching

Fig. 4. (a) Typical return screen displayed when selected the “More Information” option in the menu; (b) graph with statistics corresponding to percentage of simulated lesions inserted in phantom images.

III. RESULTS AND DATABASE COMPARISONS

Tests have been performed with the database resources and images and all of them worked well on all browsers evaluated (Internet Explorer 11 or higher, Microsoft Edge 41 or higher, Mozilla Firefox 59 or higher, Google Chrome 65 or higher, and Safari), without the need of installing any extra software or plug-ins. All tools are also available for free access at the internet database address: <http://lapimo.sel.eesc.usp.br/bancoweb/>.

BancoWeb is a public database requiring user registration (authorized by the system administrator). Other known mammography images databases do not need registration for access. MIAS [5], DDSM [4], INBreast [15] and BCDR [16] are the most known public with free access. Others however, as LLNL from UCSF [16], charges US\$ 100 for 12 CDs. Thus, a description of the main characteristics regarding such databases and BancoWeb is shown in Table 1 for comparative analysis.

Among the public databases, only BancoWeb currently is still an open project, which aims to keep developing for at least the next few years. MIAS [5] and DDSM [4] will no longer perform updates and are not responsible for any technical issues they may present.

TABLE I. MAIN MAMMOGRAPHY DATABASES COMPARISON

	MIAS	DDSM	LLNL / UCSF	Mammo Grid (CALMa)	IN Breast	BCDR	Banco Web
Year	1994	1999	2010	2001	2013	2013	2010
Country	UK	US	USA	Italy	Portugal	Portugal	BR
Number of images	322	10480	198	3369	410	1247	1700
Breast image type	Screen-film	Screen-film	Screen-film	Screen-film & FFDM	FFDM	FFDM	Screen-film & FFDM
Files	PGM	PNG	DICOM	?	DICOM	TIF	TIFF
Files access	Free	Free	Paid (US\$ 100)	Only project members	Free	Free	Free after register
Contrast resolution (bits/pixel)	8	12 (80%) 16 (20%)	12	12	12	8	12
Searching tool	No	Yes But not working	*	*	*	*	Yes
CADx classifying	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Phantom images	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes (611)
Maintenance and upgrade	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Nowadays BancoWeb contains about 1,700 images for free access on line corresponded to digitized films (by Lumiscan 50 and Lumiscan 75, Lumisys, Inc.) with 12 bits of contrast resolution and spatial resolution of 0.085mm or 0.150mm. There are also about 200 images from DR-type mammography systems. And currently 611 images from the breast phantom are also available for free downloading mainly aiming tests of image processing schemes in mammography. About 700 users are registered in the database.

The DDSM base surpasses all others in terms of number of available images. However, considering all the images in our internal base (i.e. including those not available on the network) BancoWeb has around 7,400 digital images and makes available more than 600 images from the phantom previously described. The high versatility of configurations allowed by the phantom arrangement (and hence the very large amount of different images possible to produce, with or without signals of interest), together with the single management structure designed for these images and information, is a unique tool in this field. Furthermore, it is important for the main purposes of this database – support for the development and testing of computational imaging techniques and schemes in mammography.

Until now, BancoWeb is still the only free access mammography database with a broad and functional search engine. Such a system is efficient, displays patient information, image information, clipping tools, enables classification by CADx scheme associated to the database, and allows complete download of the exam, among other features. In addition, it offers a variety of search options, enabling the user to search for a specific image or feature.

Despite being the most widely used database in the literature, the last remote update at DDSM was in 2003. The lack of a good search system makes it difficult to search for specific features considering the amount of images available.

The tools recently incorporated to BancoWeb database provides also a CADx app [17] for being used with the recorded images in any of their types (digitized or from direct digital mammography – actual breasts or phantom images). Such tool allows selecting one or two regions of interest in the image to promptly classify a nodule as suspect or not.

Finally, the novelty in this project is the system to manage registering and searching for breast phantom images provided by exposures of the phantom previously developed in our group [12]. Capable of generating several image patterns obtained by random variations of size, shape, contrast and distribution of simulated lesions, this new set can be largely used for CADx schemes tests.

IV. CONCLUSION

BancoWeb database is currently restructured so that it is prepared not only to provide – besides the actual mammography images files and respective information – registering, retrieving and downloading of breast phantom images. Comparisons of BancoWeb with other databases have shown that the requirements cited in the literature as important for a medical imaging database are met, but with the advantage of having features that other databases do not

offer up to now, such as classification with a CADx tool and availability of phantom images with randomly distribution of internal structures and backgrounds. Image searching has also been a major focus, enabling clear and objective user interaction.

In conclusion, although the system already had a variety of quality images, offering a basic set of computational tools, this work presented advances that will complement and/or improve pre-existent procedures in this database management system. In addition, a new breast phantom image set was integrated to the system in order to offer new management capabilities and digital processing of those images.

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